

ISSN 0976-5484

SOCIAL WORK JOURNAL

(BI-ANNUAL)

Volume 10

Number 2

July 2019-June 2020

Note : Due to Covid-19 both the issue are clubbed

SPECIAL ISSUE

Issues and Challenges in contemporary Social work

- Editorial - *Gopalji Mishra & Ajit Kumar Jena*
- Wellbeing of Youth and Coping during the Covid19 Pandemic - *C. Devendran*
- Construction Work, Workers and Welfare Board: A Study in Delhi - *Rohit Bharti and Prof. Sanjai Bhatt*
- Armed Conflict in Manipur and its effect on women - *Prof. Gopalji Mishra & Lojita Khaidem*
- Gandhian Philosophy on Peace and Development: Relevance for Social Work Education and Practice - *Dr. Tarun Bikash Sukai*
- Ecological and Pandemic Crises: A Cause of Structured Violence against Women - *Deepika Singh*
- Climate Change: Livelihood implications and Role of Social Workers - *Rajiv Jena*
- Crisis in Brewing Economy in Urban Tribal Community of Manipur - *Gangmei Akhuan Rongmei and MC Arunkumar*
- Single Motherhood: A Structural Perspective - *Dr. Wandaia Syngkon*
- Behind the Shadows of Public Adulation: The Private Lives of Meitei Women - *Leenabai Kshetrimayum, Ratna Huirem and Kathiresan L.*
- Vote Buying In Manipur: A Case Study On Lhangkichoi Village In Moreh Tengenoupal Sub-Division Chandel District Manipur - *Manglien Gangte*
- A study on Contributing factors to substance abuse among the clients of Silchar New Life foundation and role of social workers - *R. Lalzo S. Thangjom*
- Mat Making for Livelihood in Assam: Prospects and Retrospect - *Chayan Deb & Gangabhushan M. Molankal*
- Parenting style and its associated behavioural problems among adolescent student - *Thokchom Roda Devi & M. Tineshowri Devi*
- Health Care Facilities and Utilization of Services in Primary Health Centres of Manipur - *Mr. Nula Bethel Anal & Dr. G. Albin Joseph*
- The Unspoken Reality of Child Marriage in Durrung Tea Plantations: Social Work Intervention - *Barsha Kalit*

DEPARTMENT OF SOCIAL WORK
ASSAM UNIVERSITY, SILCHAR – 788011
Assam. INDIA. Phone: +91 3842 270821
www.aus.ac.in

Behind the Shadows of Public Adulation: The Private Lives of Meitei Women

Leenabai Kshetrimayum, Ratna Huiem and Kathiresan L.

Abstract

The position of women, their status, treatment towards them, and their levels of empowerment are clearly defined by the gendered relations, roles and responsibilities prevailing in a society. Manipur is a state in the north eastern part of India with its own rich culture and tradition where its women are assumed to enjoy independence and much empowered compared to other women in mainland India. This article is an attempt to outline the status of the married women belonging to the Meitei community which is the major ethnic group of the state. The contrasting or varying roles and responsibilities imposed on them within the private and the public spheres of their lives are what forms the focus of this paper. From early history up to the present day, women of the Meitei society are well known for their active roles and participation in the socio-economic and political aspects, which are highlighted by the existence of the 'Ima Keithel' and their roles as 'Meira Paibis'. In identifying the twist in the story of these women, the paper examines how being a traditional society with its strong cultural and traditional beliefs and practices; stigmas and concerns; married women despite being empowered in the public sphere are still kept subjugated. The veil of socially constructed norms weigh heavily on these women within the private sphere, especially in fulfilling the role of an ideal married woman. This paper identifies how women's role within the socially constructed divide of these two spheres, i.e., the private, which is marked as the women's world; and the public domain as the men's world has set a platform for women to remain vulnerable and suppressed by the gendered roles and constraints imposed on them by society.

Keywords: Private Sphere, Public Sphere, Social norms, Cultural practices, Married Meitei women

Introduction

Women in different regions of the world although belonging to different cultures have always been victims of discrimination and exploitation in one form or the other. Studies have revealed that the treatment of women and their relative power and status in society varies from culture to culture.

PhD Scholar, Department of social work, Assam University Silchar.788011

Assistant Professor, Department of social work, Assam University Silchar.788011

Assistant Professor, Department of social work, Assam University Silchar.788011

Women are also vulnerable to various forms of crimes, violence and exploitations where they are far from having an equal voice with men both within the private and public domains.

The socially constructed private and public sphere dichotomy marks women's worlds within the boundaries of the household as the private sphere; and the public domain as the natural place for men where women fear to tread. This has put women in difficult circumstances. They are suppressed under this dichotomy where they indulge in unpaid domestic work which is treated as unproductive. In the Indian society where the status of women is determined by the patriarchal norms and perspectives, the issue of women's rights and their status as a whole are always under review and scrutiny (Pateman, 1989; Rogers, 1998). Thus, there have been continuous efforts to understand ways and means to empower them and bring about gender parity. Research and activism on women's concerns have been continuously ongoing to bring about a change in their lives. However, the patriarchal instincts that are deeply rooted in society have always been a major obstruction in this process. Let us now discuss in more detail what entails this division of spheres that has been so entrenched in society.

The Private and Public Divide

The private and public sphere divide is traced back to Industrialization, where the burden of household or domestic work vis a vis the work in factories/industries came up. This revolution had created a shift from home based production to factory production, where men started to work as labor for their wages and women stayed home and indulged in unpaid domestic work which ultimately continued to carry on as a practice. Such a separation thus led to the broadening of the distinctiveness between men's work and women's work that ultimately provoked new thinking about the significance and permanence of these two distinct arenas of work. Eventually men started to go out of the house and continued to engage in the factories while women stayed at home looking after the household chores such as cooking, cleaning, taking care of children, caring for the elderly and other home based needs. As such an occupation had no visible economic returns, it came to a situation where the work in the private sphere, i.e., domestic chores and care-giving became a submissive work in comparison to the work carried out in the public sphere as economic gains were the hallmark of this type of work (Pateman, 1989).

With this valuing of paid factory work and devaluing of unpaid household work, it created pathways towards treating women to be submissive and kept under the control of men, and continue to make them

responsible for the unremunerative domestic work (Karber, 1988). The public domain which is identified as the male sphere includes the social, economic and political aspects which are regulated by the government; while the private sphere or the women's world is surrounded with responsibilities and activities confined in the realm of home, family and child rearing. The ideology of this distinction not only rationalises the exclusion of women's participation from the political and economic aspects but also helped to obscure the subordination of women within the confinement of home and family as neutral and almost like a natural occurrence. Women's actions thus continued to focus on the needs of the family that are strongly influenced by the value of domestic or the private space; while on the contrary men's actions focused on the needs of the civil society in the broader context. These thus stood to be the defining aspects of the separate spheres (Daily, 1996; Prokhovnik, 1998; Wright, 2012).

As women are kept confined within the household, their lived experiences and works are made invisible to such a large extent that their experiences, interests, actions and contributions are excluded as not worthy of politics or the civil society which automatically leads to their subjugation and negotiation (Wischermann and Muller, 2004). Men are thus found to utilize their energies on labor and politics in the public sphere of the government, the capitalist and market place and the outside world; while women are confined within the encircled space where they are expected to focus on the sentimental aspects such as relationships, emotions and the domestic works (Wright, 2012).

Feminist Inquiry and the Private Public Divide

The challengeable dichotomy of this private and public sphere has always been one of the major concerns in the context of feminist writing that had led to the rise of the feminist movement because of this harsh discrimination prevailing in the society. This distinction of the spheres has been a primary focus of feminist inquiry as the central ideology in determining women's status in their social, political and economic lives (Pateman, 1989; Daily, 1996). Higgins (1999) also adds that the ideology of these separate spheres is clearly defined by the social norms and laws and showed that the line was drawn based on gender perspectives.

Such a divide left no choice to women but to face the consequences silently without much strength to raise their voices. The confinement of women within the institution of the family has also put women in a vulnerable situation where they are being isolated and subjected under the

control of men making them prone to domestic violence (Cohen and O'Byrne, 2013). Feminists have argued that this division had brought about domestic violence; overpowering women at home and beyond. The social relationship between men and women which are underscored by this private and public divide have been under consideration since a long time which is marked as the basic arrangement of the social existence in society (Reingardiene, 2003). Hansen (1987) further argues that this dichotomy is a predetermined and socially constructed classification which are reflected on the ascribed activities given to both genders, their feminine and masculine attitudes, and the normative order, i.e., men being superior than women.

The ideology of women being tied up within the private or the perceived natural domain which includes reproduction, caring and giving emotional support to the family, are ascribed as lower than the masculine and political, i.e., the public domain. Thus as a response towards the management of economic and family life, it ultimately led to the dependence of women on men. This has brought about the underestimation of the worth of domestic works, objectified and repressed their sexuality, and resulted in the suppression of women in public discourses. Analysing both the private and public spheres simultaneously will hence help in capturing a meaningful and clear understanding about the actual experiences of women in society rather than looking at them as distinctly divided spheres.

Therefore, merely understanding the public life experiences or only the private life experiences will not be able to capture or conceptualise the actual life experiences of women in society. There is a need for analysing both the spheres simultaneously as they intersect at almost all crossroads. Likewise, in order to understand the reality about the experiences of married women in Meitei society, only looking at the public discourses is not sufficient to capture the lived experiences of these women who are projected as thoroughly balanced and have managed to unshackle themselves from the bindings of the private sphere. Hence, a composite study and understanding of what entails within the private domain is essential to understand the truth about whether such a fine balance has indeed been struck in Meitei society and the women have broken free of such a divide.

Women in Meitei Society

Women of the northeastern states of India are highly adulated and considered to be better off than their mainland counterparts because of their distinct levels of empowerment. Amongst the states in India, Manipur is popular for the boldness of women and are admired widely because of their immense

participation in the public sphere i.e, the perceived men's world. Active participation in this platform breaking the stereotypes and even excelling in this sphere of life has led to immense glorification. Amongst these women too, women of the Meitei society (the major ethnic community of Manipur), especially the married women are well known for their active participation in the public sphere which are highlighted by the existence of the *Ima Market*, famous for being the only market run totally by women and their historical role as *Meira Paibis* which is the reflection of women's bravery and dynamic involvement in the social and political aspects of the Meitei society (Barua and Devi, 2004; Devi, 2012)

Thus, several discourses outline how women of the Meitei society occupy a prominent status in the public sphere which is treated as the men's world. It is therefore worth reckoning whether their burden is reduced in the private sphere, which is in turn perceived as the women's world that revolves around the domestic household. This much adulated achievement in the public domain has thus diluted as well as hindered the understanding of the private space and the private experiences of these women. Therefore, there is an immense need to go beyond the glorified image and try to understand this difference. This paper argues that such a dichotomy is unrealistic and impractical and it is pertinent to undo these two separate spheres or at least accept that they are not mutually exclusive. Developing such a perspective is extremely important in understanding and leveraging the status of women in society.

Women's status in society is related to the social and cultural traditions, stages of economic development achieved, educational level, attitudes of society towards women, social and religious taboos, women's awareness and political attainment of women in society (Sinha and Sinha, 2013). Since the historical days, women of the Meitei society especially the married women have been playing a vital role in all spheres of their lives by being actively involved in the social, economic, political and cultural aspects of the society. Such participation mark the uniqueness of the Meitei women and it is still continuing in the present day society (Devi, 2014). Here, all the spheres of life are intended to highlight that women in spite of the active involvement in the public spheres of the society, they still play vital roles within the private sphere.

Hallmarks of the Meitei Women

The prominence of the Meitei women in the public sphere of Meitei society from the days of yore are discussed in detail below.

Nupi Lan (Women's War)

The first *Nupi Lan* or *Ahanba Nupi Lan*, 1904 took place when the political agent of Manipur Maxwell tried to reintroduce the *Lallup* (a system of forced labour for the menfolk of Manipur) which had been abolished by the then king, and also forced the people in Imphal (capital of Manipur) to rebuild the burnt house of the British agent. It was the Meitei women of Imphal who rose up in protest and fought violently with the British officials and this marked the first women's agitation. Again, the Second *Nupi Lan* or *Anisuba Nupi Lan* 1939 broke out where women filed a petition to stop the export of rice because of the prior existence of scarcity of rice in the state. But when the petition was not taken into consideration the women protested against the British officials. The protests of these women were so strong that the political agent had to close down the rice mills and the export of rice was stopped immediately (Devi, 2001). These two women's agitations are very much important in the political history of Manipur as they changed the political dimensions of the state and the women were always ready to take up mass political action of the government; which affected their interests as well as the interests of the people at large (Yambem, 1976).

The outbreak of these two women's wars have put women of the Meitei society in a position where they are highly adulated and glorified. Such a glorification has put up a belief about the lives of Meitei women in general that they are brave and they possess high qualities of leadership which is indubitable (Devi, 2012). Ensuring these outbreaks, Meitei women now for generations have followed the trend of always coming to the forefront with regard to any form of protest or agitation against the government or any unacceptable situation that occurs in the society.

Role as Meira Paibis (Torch Bearers)

The legend of the two women's wars has thus become a tradition of women's active participation in any form of injustice or social evils that comes up in the society. This had also led to the formation of the women's groups of *Meira Paibis* who are always at the forefront to deal with the social evils and disturbances that exist in the society. This women organisation which continues to be an important part of Meitei society were earlier known as *Nisha Bandis* (women's voluntary group for anti-liquor) which later on took an active role in punishing the youths who are drug addicts and/ or indulge in thefts or crimes. The role of *Meira Paibis* is thus very significant within the Meitei society. Whenever discussion or talks on Meitei society are addressed, *Meira Paibis* always come into consideration as they are a part of the image

of the brave Meitei women, who have been emboldened enough to take on anti-social activities. The *Meira Paibi* movement started as a voluntary organisation of the womenfolk to prevent violation of human rights of the people in the hands of the armed forces. Their movement emerged stronger against human rights violation in the state of Manipur which has been declared as disturbed area under the Armed forces special powers act, 1958 since 1980 (Devi, 2001; Devi, 2012; Sudhir, 2013).

Being a state ridden with insurgency and underdevelopment, many conflict situations arise and therefore many protests and violent agitations have taken place which were always led by women. Women would emerge at the forefront without any hesitation and take it as their full responsibility. The role of these women came to the spotlight in a particular incident of the brutal murder case of a 32 years old woman, Thangjam Manorama, whose body was found mutilated and bullet ridden, allegedly by 17th Assam Rifles troops. In strong condemnation of the horrific inhuman violence, twelve women protested naked in front of the noted *Kangla Fort* with the slogan, “*Indian Army Rape Us*”. This incident shook the world; which in turn again focused the lens on the bravados of the Meitei women (Naorem, 2015). Such unimagined feats being achieved by the women’s movement in Manipuri society, particularly, the Meiteis, distinctly highlighted how Meitei women actively participate in the public sphere.

The Ima Market (Women’s Market)

Along with the roles played by the Meitei women in the political aspects, their economic independence and authority in the field of trade and business also had a major presence in the public discourses of these women. Such active participation and contribution in the economic aspects has been witnessed by the existence of this market. The *Ima Market* or the women’s market is the only market run exclusively by married women the world over. This is the place where women not only carry out trade and business. It is also the spot where women share and discuss about the social and political happenings in the state. This has been the scenario ever since the King’s regime, when Manipur was a princely state, before it merged with the Indian Union in 1949. This market was the place which supported the outbreak of the famous *Nupi Lan*. It plays a significant role in the socio-economic life of these women which sets a glaring example of women’s independent roles and the maintenance of an indigenous system which is also reflected in the presence of various cottage industries.

The control and ownership of the market by these women not only showed their involvement or participation in economic growth and their economic independence, but also the upliftment of their status within the society as a whole (Sinha and Sinha, 2013). The potential of the Meitei women to excel in all the aspects of society, be it social, economic or political and their capability to combat any form of imposition made on them have made these women an illustrious example of an empowered and independent woman, celebrated and glorified by all (Rajput, 2013). Such has been the discourse about Meitei women and their public excellence that their private woes remained in the shadows, ignored and unstudied.

Thus, so far, it is pertinent to underline that all the above discussions have illustrated how Meitei women have been walking the hallowed spaces that are perceived as the male domain. This has somehow led to an uninformed imagination that Meitei women do not suffer at all from the woes of patriarchy. To dispel this myth of men and women walking hand in hand in Meitei society as equals, we shall look at the private sphere that Meitei women inhabit.

The Private Sphere and Meitei Women

Very few discourses on the private life experiences of these women are available. This itself points to the sheer lack of understanding about their private lives, shrouded as they are by the public discourses of their achievements. There is no doubt that Meitei society too is a patriarchal society, as are societies across the world; where men hold more power and command over women. Because of this hierarchical system that prevails in the society, women are being suppressed and kept inferior to men despite their active participation in the socio-economic and political aspects. Though Meitei women are stated to have a considerably free position within society, gender inequality exists as women are kept under the control of men who are regarded as the head of the family (Irene, 2004; Devi, 2011).

The various customs and traditions, rituals and practices enacted with the advent of Hinduism were always in favour of the menfolk. The identification of women as someone who should be devoted to her husband and remain under the control of the male counterparts were imposed to the women in the Meitei society (Singh, 2006). Below are presented some illustrations that throw light on the prevalence of patriarchy in Meitei society.

Socio-cultural configuration

The status and treatment of women to a large extent is the product of the past socio-cultural configuration (Parvin, 2014). No matter how far they progress,

women are always bound by the socio-cultural boundaries with various sanctions imposed on them. Women of the Meitei society no matter how far they excel in the public sphere they are not exempted from the domestic works. They have to fulfil the role of a mother, wife and daughter-in-law and engage in all household domestic chores, child rearing and care giving. Men while excelling in the public sphere are not given compulsion to engage in the household but for women it is made a compulsion to fulfil their duties as a married woman.

As a tradition, women are expected to keep the house neat and clean, expected to be early risers before any menfolk of the family wakes, and are also expected to do all the cleaning and household chores. Such a classification of work also leads to oppression and discrimination which are otherwise treated as insignificant. Women struggle to fulfil all these imposed roles but their contribution is generally not taken into consideration especially the caring and rearing aspects in the home front. Thus, as they juggle between home and life outside, especially in the case of working women, the burden just gets heavier. It has rarely been a tradition that the menfolk lend a helping hand in domestic chores. This shows a deep divide where domesticity and its related affairs are thrust upon the women owing its roots to patriarchy. No amount of participation by women in the public sphere seemed to affect or reduce the expectations of women's roles that has to be rigidly performed and observed in the domestic or private sphere.

Patriarchal Influence

The dominant mindset of patriarchy strongly impacts the status of women. The status and the image of women came to be reflected by the two Hindu women idols, namely, Sita and Draupadi as depicted in the epics of Ramayana and Mahabharata, where the ideals of womanhood are framed from a male perspective. With this system being implemented men enjoy the advantage of being superior. The mythical divide that men's world is within the public domain only has exempted them from engaging in the domestic chores. However, in case of women they are bound to balance both the spheres. Despite the remarkable participation in the public domain and being awarded respect and honour and glorified in the public sphere, there is rapid increase in the reportage of violence on women within the private domains too (Irene, 2014). The deeply sown seeds of patriarchy in the Meitei society have not enabled women in this society to free themselves from violence and discrimination but rather continue to be the victims of mental, physical and sexual violence (Laltlinzo and Beeju, 2017). As women are bound to serve and take responsibility of the men, violence done on them are suffered

silently by the women and it is treated as normal. The internalisation of this harsh patriarchal influence has made women oppressed and discriminated and this has been going on for generations behind the camouflage of public adulation of their bravados.

Unequal workload distribution has also placed women in a state of exploitation in one sense to fulfil the role as responsible women and at the same time excel in the public domain. Multitasking with workloads all round the clock is the reality these women have to undergo. Absence of equal distribution of household chores and corresponding responsibilities added to various forms of domestic violence is the harsh reality women face within the private domain. The social structures already designed in favour of men derived from the patriarchal patronage continues to obstruct women despite their massive contributions to society (Irene, 2014). Hence such public adulations appear to be a farce in the midst of private agony.

Traditional practice and beliefs

The traditional practice and beliefs which impose women with several constraints is one of the major causes for the submission of women's status in the society which are not taken into account as a form of oppression. They are neutralised and implanted in the mindset of the people and are to be followed without any questions raised. Many less explored or neglected superstitious beliefs, taboos and traditional practices had kept these women suppressed and discriminated. There are several instances of the beliefs regarding prohibition of touching and handling of women's clothes by male members where it is treated as unusual and sacrilege if men happen to do so. Thus the ideology of purity and pollution is of concern in understanding the lives of these women. During menstruation they are treated as impure or polluted or dirty where they are restricted from going inside the kitchen or get in touch with any male member of the family. During the time of childbirth, the new mother is treated as impure or polluted and kept isolated from other male members of the family. The new mother is not allowed to touch or move freely within the house. The ideal logic behind keeping women from doing any form of common work was to make the new mother rest properly, but this isolation attempts more towards subjugation rather than giving care and protection to the women (Singh, 2006; Devi, 2013).

Another belief that is biased against women is the concept regarding *Phanek* (traditional women attire worn by wrapping around the waist). The *Phanek* is treated as an untouchable by the male and it is advised not to hang or dry this garment at places where it will be visible when male members of

the family go out of the house as it is treated as bad luck. The garment is restricted to be washed with other clothes of men. But this same *Phanek* if it belongs to an elderly, i.e., the mother of the male than it is regarded as very pure and sacred where men even carry a piece of the garment inside a talisman known as *Jantra* in the local dialect which is believed to give protection to them. Interestingly and contrastingly, the same garment which is sacred to the sons is again a bad omen to the husband or any other men. The notion behind the custom of understanding *Phanek* as polluted or untouchable if seen from a hygienic perspective, may mean that it might be stained with menstrual blood or vaginal discharge which are considered impure. But the problem is that it is taken from the perspective of only being impure or polluted which is attached with a sense of inauspiciousness to sight or touch regardless of its state of cleanliness or being dirty (Ningombam, 2015).

There is also a very petty sounding but significant thing. It is the practice of men being given the chance to enjoy *Chakmai* (*the uppermost portion of cooked rice*) whereas women only get the lower portion somehow carries the imagery that men are superior to women. Yet another instance is where men are not allowed to eat the leftover of women but women are made to eat or can eat the leftovers of men and also women are not allowed to touch while the male members of the family are having food (Basanta, 2010). Interestingly, women on the very first day of her marriage is made to eat the leftover food of her husband after he has finished from the same plate and this custom still continues to this day without understanding the meaning or the purpose of the act. The problem is with the underlying meaning that the act carries. It symbolises the wife's subordinate position to her husband which adheres to the logic of man's domination both physically and psychologically (Ningombam, 2015). These practices and beliefs which are very much deeply embedded in the mindsets of the people despite the modern scientific education and development has least succeeded in putting an end to these practices from the society which have been passed on from generations. These traditional practices and beliefs which are the outcome of the cultural configurations in maintaining and preserving archaic traditions need to be explored in the right perspective so as to gain a better understanding about the lived experiences of married Meitei women.

Undoing the Private Public Divide

From all the above discussions and the illustrations about Meitei women, we can clearly see that the life experiences undergone within these two spheres are starkly different. The socio-cultural practices enlisted above maybe

belittled as mere travesty but they indeed weigh heavily on the shoulders of the Meitei woman. It has therefore to be accepted and emphasized that the public sphere and the private sphere traverse and intersect upon each other at all points and cannot under any terms be treated as distinctly different from each other. The lived experiences in both the spheres have a different story to tell as can be seen from the above discussions. Hence, in understanding the status of these women, a composite and simultaneous analysis and study of experiences in both the spheres of their lives is important. A thorough and deeper understanding of the cultural beliefs and practices, social stigmas and taboos existing within the community is necessary which has a great influence in directing and regulating the actions and behaviour of the society which is mandatory for both genders. The patriarchal nature of society has built a deeply entrenched divide between these two spheres, which are almost synonymous with gender roles. The unspoken truth remains that Meitei women too continue to compromise and bear the burden despite the “red carpet” of glorification and adulation in their public world. No doubt, because of their active participation in the public domain, it has created a spotlight for them in comparison with the women in other societies. However, we conclude by highlighting that their daily life experiences within the private domain need to be duly explored as it will indeed unravel a plethora of hidden realities and experiences of these much glorified Meitei women.

References

- Barua, I., & Devi, A. (2004). Women Market of Manipur: An Anthropological Historical Perspective. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 15(2), 129-133.
- Basanta, N. (2010). *Meitei Family in Flux: An Empirical Study*. New Delhi: Akansha Publishing House.
- Cohen, R., & O'Byrne, S. (2013). “Can You Hear Me Now... Good!” Feminism (s), the Public/Private Divide, and Citizens United v. FEC. *UCLA Women's Law Journal*, 20(1), 39-70.
- Daily, A. C. (1996). Lochner for Women: The Ideology of Separate Spheres in Muller v. Oregon. *Faculty Articles and Papers*. 293. (Retrieved from https://opencommons.uconn.edu/law_papers/293).
- Devi, K. B. (2001). The role of Women in Manipur Politics. In Thomas, C. J, Gopalkrishnan. R., Singh, R. K. R. (Eds.). *Constraints in Development of Manipur*.(pp. 113-131).New Delhi: Regency Publications.
- Devi, K. S. (2013). *Child Rearing in Manipur Meitei, Muslims and Tribes*. New Delhi: Mittal Publication.

- Devi, N. P. (2011). *The Cultural History of Early Manipur*. Manipur: Times Publishing House Manipur.
- Devi, R. K. H. (2012). *Women and Socio-Political Movements: In Recent Pasts and Present Manipur*. New Delhi: Sunmarg Publishers and Distributors.
- Devi, S.U. (2014). Determinants of Development among Women in Manipur. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19(10), 23-25.
- Devi, S.U. (2014). Determinants of Development among Women in Manipur. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19(10), 23-25.
- Hansen, K. V. (1987). Feminist Conceptions of Public and Private: A Critical Analysis. *Berkeley Journal of Sociology*, 32, 105-128.
- Higgins, T. E. (1999). Reviving the Public/Private Distinction in Feminist Theorising Symposium on Unfinished Feminist Business. *FLASH: The Fordham Law of Scholarship and History*, 75 (847), 847-867.
- Irene, S. (2014). *Women of Manipur: An Alternative Perspective*. New Delhi: Akansha Publishing House.
- Kerber, L. K. (1988). Separate Spheres, Female Worlds, Women's Place: The Rhetoric of Women's History. *The Journal of American History*, 75(1), 9-39.
- Lalitinzo, G., & Beeju, K. (2017). *Violence Against Women in North East India*. New Delhi: Akansha Publishing House.
- Naorem, D. (2015). Motherhood and the politics of Resistance. In Henthoiba, L. & Churchill, S. (Eds.), *Cultural Practices and Identity Politics in Manipur*.(pp. 141-154). New Delhi: Concept Publishing Company Pvt. Ltd.
- Ningombam, S. (2015). Mapping Repressive practices against women in the Meitei society. In Henthoiba, L. & Churchill, S. (Eds.), *Cultural Practices and Identity Politics in Manipur*.(pp.129-140). New Delhi: Concept Publishing Company Pvt. Ltd.
- Parvin, M. R. (2012). *Empowerment of Women Strategies & Systems for Gender Justice*. New Delhi: Dominant Publishers and Distributors Pvt Ltd.
- Pateman, C. (1989). *The Disorder of Women: Democracy, feminism, and political theory*. Cambridge: Basil Blackwell Ltd.
- Prokhovnik, R. (1998). Public and Private Citizenship: From Gender Invisibility to Feminist Inclusiveness. *Feminist Review*, 60(1), 84-104.
- Rajput, M. (2012). Social Economic and Political Status of Manipur. In Madhu Rajput (ed.).*Social and Cultural Stratification in North East India*. New Delhi: Manak Publication Pvt. Ltd.
- Reingardiene, J. (2003). Dilemmas in Private/Public Discourse Contexts for Gender-based Violence against Women in Lithuania. *Journal of Baltic Studies*, 30(3), 354-368.
- Rogers, M. F. (1998). Clearence Thomas, Patriarchal Discourse and Public/Private Spheres. *The Sociological Quarterly*, 39(2), 289-308.

Social Work Journal (Bi-annual), Dept. of Social Work, AUS

- Singh, N.G. (2006). *The Meitei Society: A study on Traditional Life Circle Ceremonies*. New Delhi: Akansha Publishing House.
- Sinha, H., & Sinha, S. (2013). *Women in North East India: Status, Empowerment and Development Perspectives*. New Delhi: Akansha Publishing House.
- Sudhir, H. (2013). *Market and State: Women's Political Participation in Manipur In Historical Perspective*. New Delhi: Sunmarg Publishers and Distributors.
- Wischemann, U., & Muller, I. (2004). Feminist Theories on the Separation of the Private and Public: Looking Back, Looking Forward. *Women in German Yearbook*, 20, 184-197.
- Wright, D.C. (2012). Theorising History: Separate Spheres, The Public/Private Binary and a New Analytic for Family Law History. *ANZLH E-Journal*, 44(2), 44-77.
- Yambem, S. (1976). Nupilan: Manipur Women's Agitation, 1939. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 11(8), 325-331.